

Deep SSL Inspection with Active Directory Integration

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Abstract—SSL Inspection is a new concept on the network security that divides the opinion about its use. Some are with the idea that it is an absurd idea and others are very convinced that's the last measure for network protection. There are little who are in the middle of this opinion. SSL Inspection is also called TLS/HTTPS Interception.

Keywords – SSL (Secure Socket Layer); Network Security; SSL Inspection; Active Directory; TLS/HTTPS Interception.

I. INTRODUCTION

HTTPS is a combined protocol of HTTP (Hyper Text Markup Protocol) and the SSL (Secure Socket Layer)/TLS (Transport Layer Protocol), it has the features of HTTP with the authentication and encryption from SSL/TLS that enables the protection of HTTP communication. This is very important as the information that we send is transferred from one device to another before it arrives on the final destination server. Since credit card numbers, usernames and passwords are very sensitive information, must not be seen by intermediate devices, it has not to be transferred in clear text over HTTP. This type of information must be encrypted and protected by SSL and only the final server can read the information.

Since the beginning of the SSL it has been misused in different ways to hide and spread dangerous content. In these days almost all of the website use HTTPS including bank website, social media, underground forums etc., so it has been a must to control and inspect this kind of traffic. SSL/TLS Inspection is the best solution to provide the

control and inspection of HTTPS in other word is the process of intercepting SSL/TLS connection between two endpoints. Interception is realized from a well-known technique man-in-the-middle (MiTM), without the permission of both ends, it's executed between the client and server.

At first sight SSL/TLS Inspection compromises the purpose of HTTPS but it's more complicated than it looks. When we navigate to our social network pages, we see that all of them are protected with SSL/TLS and this helps us to protect our sensitive information. The sensitive information is encrypted to a particular secure format and it's transferred on that secure format until it arrive on the final server. Social media and bank accounts are not the only that use SSL/TLS and the use of SSL/TLS is not always clear and shining. Together with appropriate information over SSL/TLS can be transferred dangerous content. Within SSL/TLS can be hidden viruses, spyware, and other malware that may do a lot of damage in the organization. Attacking with SSL/TLS is very common in the modern world with around 50% of all attacks.

SSL/TLS Inspection purpose is to scan and analyze all of the content inside SSL/TLS and then filter the potential dangerous content. This method is called Full SSL Inspection / Deep SSL Inspection, it has the features of: antivirus, web filtering, email filtering etc.

II. RELATED WORKS

Different studies has been made on SSL Inspection and most of them have analyzed the solutions offered by

different vendors. Still no study on SSL Inspection with AD integration and no study on end user results.

L.Waked, M. Mannan, A. Youssef [4] have presented a framework for analyzing TLS interception of network appliance to detect vulnerabilities. They have tested thirteen network appliance (boxes) and discovered that all of their TLS proxies are vulnerable to different levels. Also the clients behind these boxes are vulnerable to MiTM attacks. Three of these boxes rely on pre-generated root keys allowing MiTM attacks.

S. Ruoti, M. O'Neill, D. Zappala, K. E. Seamons [8] have realized the first survey of general user attitudes toward TLS proxies. The opinions are divided on security, privacy and attacks from hackers or government surveillance. Most of them are concerned about the malicious user of SSL/TLS for identity theft, some of them would react negatively and some will change behavior when they realize that their traffic is intercepted. Some of the users has lost the concept of privacy.

K. Bhargavan, G. Leurent. On the practical (in-) security of 64-bit block ciphers: Collision attacks on HTTP over TLS and OpenVPN [7] have analyzed the block ciphers on some internet protocols such as TLS, SSH and IPsec. They have realized that with the block ciphers that they use are vulnerable to collision attacks and to avoid this one it's better to use AES over 3DES. They suggest to use 128-bit block ciphers instead of 64-bit. They suggest some measures to prevent these attacks.

Z. Durumeric, Z. Ma, D. Springall, R. Barnes, N. Sullivan, E. Bursztein, M. Bailey, J. A. Halderman, V. Paxson. The security impact of HTTPS interception [5] have analyzed the security impact on HTTPS Interception in the wild. They have noticed that 62% of all traffic that is intercepted has reduced security and 58% of this traffic has different vulnerabilities. They have found that interception is spread on all corporates and the security concerns exist almost everywhere.

X. Carnavalet, M. Mannan. Killed by Proxy: Analyzing Client-end TLS Interception Software [6] have proposed a framework for evaluation of client-end TLS proxies, by addressing limitations of regular TLS test suites and adding more test specifically relevant to this kind of proxies. They have used this framework to analyze fourteen different antivirus and parental control applications with TLS proxy abilities. They have found that all of the TLS proxy implementation are vulnerable to their test, while some are vulnerable to man-in-the-middle attacks as soon as the product is installed on the system. This implementation should be more carefully integrated and developed and they put in question the use of this software especially in case of antiviruses that have the purpose to protect users from different malicious attacks.

III. How SSL/TLS INSPECTION DOES WORKS?

SSL/TLS Inspection or HTTPS Interception is the process of controlling the traffic over HTTPS (SSL/TLS) in simpler words is the process of filtering out the dangerous content from HTTPS (SSL/TLS) through man-in-the-middle (MiTM) attacks.

SSL/TLS Inspection is realized with the help of an interception device located between two final endpoints and all the traffic passes through this device. When the intercept or locates a HTTPS (SSL/TLS) connection, it intercept the traffic, decrypt this encrypted connection and then scans it and establishes a connection with the client or server. Real world scenario for inbound traffic.

Using this method, the Interceptor impersonates the recipient of the SSL session, decrypts and finally inspects the content. The Interceptor encrypts the content again, creates a new SSL session between itself and the recipient of the content, impersonating the sender and sends the content to the recipient as per Figure 1.

Figure 1. HTTPS Interception Diagram

IV. NETWORK DIAGRAM AND APPLIANCE CONFIGURATION

For this study we have used a very complex network infrastructure with more than 350 host where all of devices are duplicated. As it's described on the Figure 2. Logical Network Diagram we have our office located in Tirana and it's connected with the Milan office by two layer2 connection that are used as load balancer and failover creating a MLPS, we have an internet connection with ISP Provider (ABCOM). All of the hosts are managed from our FortiGate 500E Firewall.

Figure 2. Logical Network Diagram

The ASR920-01 and ASR920-02 routers can be reached by the FortiGate 500E through the use of BDI interfaces, connected to the Nexus 3064 in HA thanks to the use of the

VPC. In normal conditions, traffic to our servers and CPEs is rotated to the Huawei Backbone and carried through the L2 Prov.1 and Prov.2 links. Internet traffic is routed through ABCOM by the ASR920-02 router. In the event of a Fault on the ASR920-02 router, the traffic destined toward servers and internet traffic are routed by the Huawei Backbone and an Italian IP is used for the NAT of the connections. This mode is also used for the accessibility of some websites, available only to Italian users. In the event of an ASR920- 01 router fault, the traffic designated to our servers is routed by the Huawei Backbone and the internet traffic is routed by our ISP (ABCOM).

The FortiGate, authenticates the user transparently and allows access to all network resources based on their Active Directory groups. This means that users who are already logged into the AD will not view the Captive Portal while browsing and their browsing will be guaranteed thanks to the "Single Sign-On". To achieve this goal, the FSSO Agent software is installed on each DC Domain Albania, appropriately configured to "intercept" from the Event Viewer, the login events relating to users of the "DomainAlbania.com" domain.

Figure 3. FortiGate FSSO Login

Thanks to the use of the SSO, user navigation has been appropriately filtered based on their AD Group, thus satisfying the requests of the Team Leaders and globally preventing navigation to URLs considered to be "high risk". Categories blocked for all types of users: Porn, Violence, and Proxy.

Figure 4. FortiGate Web Filtering

To make sure all encrypted traffic is properly inspected, it is used "Deep Inspection". Using this method, the FortiGate impersonates the recipient of the SSL session, decrypts and finally inspects the content. The FortiGate encrypts the content again, creates a new SSL session

between itself and the recipient of the content, impersonating the sender and sends the content to the recipient.

The CA certificate used by FortiGate is that of ARACNOS. Banking and Finance categories are excluded from SSL-Inspection to avoid winning into problems due to the different chain of certificates.

Figure 5. FortiGate Deep SSL Inspection

The Fortinet Security Fabric is the component of Fortinet that allows the visualization of the security status of the entire network [1]. It is an open ecosystem, which can also be integrated with third-party systems and therefore not with the Fortinet brand. The integration and visibility of third-party systems allows the FortiGate, through the AI (Artificial Intelligence), to manage events within the network and independently perform remediation actions when certain conditions are present, e.g. an Infected Host. Currently, through the Security Fabric, it is possible to view and block hosts that carry out "malicious" traffic.

Figure 6. Fortinet Security Fabric

V. RESULTS

After we have configured as explained above, we have performed some tests on different users and groups inside our organization. After the users login on computer with their active directory user we notice on our firewall that it has been logged in with the Single Sign-On method.

Figure 7. Single Sign-On

After the Single Sign-On we verify the certificates used from the client for an HTTPS website and a bank website.

We notice that all websites use the certificate generated from The Interception and bank websites use the bank certificate.

Figure 8. Certificate

We have tested the certificate generated from The Interceptor and it is a valid and trusted certificate. It uses TLS 1.2 with AES 125-bit encryption.

Figure 9. Certificate Validation

We have reviewed our appliance configuration and the certificate is verified and the appliance is using up to date algorithms, is updated to the latest version and we have applied the latest patch.

Figure 10. Appliance Configuration

We have configured users that our appliance is not performing SSL Inspection and they go in clear for every

website they visit. We have tested some of this users and even they are on Single Sign-On, we have bypassed the SSL Inspection.

User Name #	Method #	Duration #	Traffic Volume #	Issued by: *admin
1	Fortinet Single Sign-On	11 days, 6 hours, 59 minutes and 14 seconds	30.83 GB	Issued by: 07/04/21

Figure 11. Users that bypass SSL Inspection

With our appliance we have configured the Forti Analyzer which include: Log View, SOC, Incidents & Events, Reports etc. On the picture below we see a list of top 10 threats that has been blocked by our firewall on the last week.

Figure 12. Top 10 Threats

Also we have generated a list of all compromised hosts that our system has captured.

#	Host Name	Last Detected	OS	Verdict	# of Threats
1	172.16.22.207	2020-02-28 12:41:33	Windows 10	Blocked	1
2	172.16.22.134	2020-02-28 12:50:53	Windows 10	Blocked	1
3	172.16.19.138	2020-02-28 10:16:22	Windows 10	Blocked	1
4	10.47.172.16.22.1771	2020-02-24 14:32:06	Windows 10	Blocked	1
5	172.16.22.481	2020-02-24 11:34:29	Windows 10	Blocked	1
6	172.16.20.22	2020-02-19 12:44:04	Windows 10	Blocked	1
7	172.16.22.190	2020-02-12 16:50:48	Windows 10	Blocked	1
8	172.16.22.35	2020-02-05 17:42:38	Windows 10	Blocked	1
9	172.16.19.221	2020-01-31 09:51:44	Windows 10	Blocked	1

#	Detect Pattern	Threat Type	Threat Name
1	www.sblogkyoo.com	Malware	CnC

Host Name	Destination IP	Service	Action
www.sblogkyoo.com	88.221.111.50	HTTPS	blocked

Figure 13. Compromised Hosts

VI. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

We have tested the Single Sign-On feature of our system and as we checked below all of the users that are logged in with an Active Directory Users are automatically identified on our firewall. For the machines that are not part of Active Directory we are able to login with captive portal so we can continue to navigate but we have to install the ARACNOS certificate manually. We are using this case for all of our MAC Users that are not in active directory.

We have tested the bank websites as we have configured to bypass the SSL Inspection for all bank websites as it may occur to problems due to the different chain of certificates. As the results showed the bank website is opened with its original certificate and the other website that goes on SSL is with ARACNOS certificate.

We have checked the certificate with google chrome and we see that the certificate is valid and trusted. Our certificate uses TLS 1.2, ECDHE RSA with P-256, and

AES_128_GCM which are all patched with not known bugs or vulnerabilities.

We have checked our appliance configuration and settings and it results with all of the certificates validated, up to dated and with support from the vendor, all of the services are enabled: IPS, Antivirus, and Web Filtering.

We have verified users that are on Active Directory but we have configured them in mode so they can bypass the SSL Inspection. These are VIP users and we don't want that their traffic to be intercepted.

We have generated some charts from our SOC that's inside our box. From the results we see that most of them are blocked connections from hosts that want to contact with unknown servers to download and upload data. This connections are blocked from our firewall and we are happy to see that our network is secure without dangerous content spread and a clear sheet on information leakage and espionage.

Also we have generated a list of all compromised hosts that are on our network. We can notice that even with SSL Inspection enabled some of our computers are infected with spyware and malware. Infected hosts are from users that have the SSL Inspection enabled.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the studies more than 10% of all HTTPS web connections are intercepted by security "software" through SSL/TLS Inspection. This offers a good layer of protection for the individual or the company but as some researches show they make them more vulnerable. The question is why?

In theory these "software" have reasons to intercept SSL/TLS connections, they decrypt the connection to detect dangerous traffic or hidden threats. Also they are used to monitor incoming and outgoing traffic to avoid data leak or to protect the network users from any kind of dangerous attacks like: hidden threats, data loss and theft, user location etc. As we explained in this research if the configuration is implemented correctly it prevents a lot of damage. What happen if there are misconfigurations?

All of this products are using man-in-the-middle (MiTM) network analyzing technique, this MiTM machines or software are placed between the client and the server. They decrypt the SSL/TLS connection using a certificate, analyze the traffic and then encrypt it back using another SSL/TLS certificate. Sometimes the certificates are self-signed and are installed to the user machine by network administrator on the user machine. The second SSL/TLS connection is very often less secure then the first. The error on this one is from

vendors or from network administrator. The vendor use outdated encryption methods or do not validate the certificates or do not patch the SSL/TLS security holes or use insecure SSL/TLS configurations.

Based on this we have arrived in some conclusions for the vendors and network administrator:

- Use updated encryption methods.
- Validate all of your certificates.
- Patch on regularly basis the SSL/TLS holes.
- Review machines or software configuration.
- Always install verified and update certificates on user machines.

In these days most of SSL/TLS machines or software are not configured correctly and they are making systems more vulnerable, their performance is lower and they are risking user privacy. In the future years we can put in practice new methods and configuration to have more secure SSL/TLS Inspection machines and software. We can analyze today's errors from vendors or network administrator. SSL/TLS Inspection methods should include integration with third parties like Microsoft Active Directory.

Currently 80% of enterprise traffic is encrypted and it has an increasing of 15% per year so in a couple of years all of the enterprise traffic will be encrypted and we should be able to offer new SSL/TLS Inspection methods without sacrificing security and performance.

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